

STOP!

- × Is it blurry?
- × Is it far away?
- × Is it wet?

It is **not** identifiable!

Do Not Post!

iNaturalist is an online community where anyone interested in nature can post observations of the natural world. After peer-review identification, observations are considered Research Grade and are considered high enough quality to be used in scientific research.

Lichens are the cooperative partnership between a fungus and an algae or bacterium. The body of a lichen is made of fungus that keeps a thin layer of the partner inside of it. The partner photosynthesizes and provides the fungus with nutrients.

You can find iNaturalist at
<https://www.inaturalist.org/>
 or iPhone & Android apps

How to make great lichen observations on iNaturalist

By Eli Denzer

GO!

- × Is it in focus?
- × Is it well lit?
- × Can you see all parts?

It is **identifiable!**

Post It!

Award #2115191
 Award #2436848

NYS Museum New York State

Take clear well lit pictures.

To be useful in research, pictures must be high quality. Try and get the lighting and color balance of images as true to life as possible. Take as many pictures as needed. **Do not post images that are shaky, blurry, or taken too far away..**

- Close up
- Detailed
- Middle and edges visible
- Out of focus
- Obscured

Take pictures when subject is dry.

Moisture can drastically change the appearance of a lichen. When wet the upper layer of a lichen turns somewhat transparent, making the green algal layer visible. This green hue obscures the dry color required for identification.

Limit amount of disturbance

The best thing about iNaturalist is the ability to record observations with only photographs. Limit the amount of disturbance caused when taking pictures. Do not collect specimens unless explicitly allowed to do so and limit exposing the underside to a very small section to limit damage.

Take multiple pictures in multiple magnifications from all angles.

Get head on, the edges, the middle, and the underside if possible. A hand lens can be held up to a camera lens (DSLR and mobile phone) to get increased magnification.

Record the substrate

What a lichen is growing on is an important identification characteristic. Record what the species is growing on as specifically as one is able.

For example tree species, rock type, moisture levels, etc.

Limit reliance on AI

iNaturalist will automatically try and identify organisms in photos. Do not automatically trust these predictions. While using AI identification can be tempting, algorithms are a poor choice for lichens. Small datasets and obscure details mean that AI identifications are often incorrect.